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The influence of environmental dimensions on customer attraction in sport complexes 'Responsive Environments (Case study: Enghelab sport complex)

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Abstract: Sporting venues as a social space in which individuals are directly related, to better performance and higher income, are needed to attract more customers. The main objective of this study was to investigate the effect of environmental features of sport areas on attracting customers with respect to the concept of responsive environments. Research method was descriptive- comparative study. The statistical population was all members of Enghelab sport complex (N=20000). Base on Morgan table, 350 people were selected to this research. 25 question research made questionnaire was used to collect data. Reliability of the questionnaire was determined by α -Cronbach that was reached 0/81. In this study from seven dimensions of responsive environments, permeability, legibility, variety, robustness, visual appropriateness and richness had significant relationship with customer attraction in Enghelab sport complex. Also, permeability was the most important dimension. Easy accessibility to the places of Enghelab sport complex, offering various services to the people and also attractive environment of sport area was the factors that have positive influence on customer's choice.

Key Words: Sport arena, Enghelab sport complex, Environmental dimensions, Customer, Responsive environments

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